

PREVENTION OF NEURO-MENTAL STRESS IN FUTURE GENERAL PRACTITIONERS

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Introduction. Today, the socio-psychological components of the professional activity of general practitioners, its stressfulness, remain without due attention of researchers. Specialists from various industries are trying to give meaning to the very concept of a general practitioner and, on this basis, to determine its main functions, problematic aspects. However, as practice shows, there is a lack of a unified approach to this problem [1,2,3,4,6]

Purpose of the study: To determine the dynamics of the level of manifestation of neuropsychic stress in future general practitioners before and after the training program.

Material and methods of research: For the purposes of the study, the dynamics of the level of manifestation of neuropsychic tension in future general practitioners was revealed, an empirical study was organized and conducted, in which 98 future general practitioners, third, fourth and fifth years of study, as female, as well as male. To achieve the goal, a questionnaire for determining the neuropsychic stress of T.A. Nemchina[5].

Result and discussion. The analysis of the results of the first and second psychodiagnostic examinations showed that, following the results of the training program, the future general practitioners of the experimental group (n=98) significantly improved the severity of the previously identified complex of individual psychological characteristics interpreted as a group of personal determinants of professional stress. Thus, the number of respondents with a high level of manifestation of neuropsychic stress (diagnosed using the Questionnaire for determining neuropsychic stress by T.A. Nemchin) decreased from 50% (49 people - before the training program) to 8.2% (8 people - after the program of training sessions). Accordingly, future general practitioners with an average and low level of manifestation of neuropsychic stress increased from 50% (49 people - before the training program) to 91.8% (90 people - after the training program).

Figure 1. Dynamics of the level of neuropsychic tension in the experimental group of future practitioners before and after training sessions (n=98)

Conclusion: As a result, the level of manifestation of neuropsychic stress decreased in future general practitioners.

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